

Functional hydrogels as therapeutic tools for spinal cord injury: New perspectives on immunopharmacological interventions

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ARTICLE INFO

Available online 20 November 2021

Editor: S.J. Enna

Keywords:

Spinal cord injury
Neuroinflammation
Hydrogel
Immunomodulation
Drug delivery
Controlled release

ABSTRACT

Spinal cord injury (SCI) is a complex medical and psychological challenge for which there is no curative therapy currently available. Despite major progress in pharmacological and surgical approaches, clinical trials for SCI patients have been uniformly disappointing thus far as there are many practical and biological issues yet to be resolved. Neuroinflammation is a critical event of the secondary injury phase after SCI, and recent research strategies have focused on modulating the immune response after injury to provide a more favorable recovery environment. Biomaterials can serve this purpose by providing physical and trophic support to the injured spinal cord after SCI. Of all potential biomaterials, functional hydrogels are emerging as a key component in novel treatment strategies for SCI, including controlled and localized delivery of immunomodulatory therapies to drive polarization of immune cells towards a pro-regenerative phenotype. Here, we extensively review recent developments in the use of functional hydrogels as immunomodulatory therapies for SCI. We briefly describe physicochemical properties of hydrogels and demonstrate how advanced fabrication methods lead to the required heterogeneity and hierarchical arrangements that increasingly mimic complex spinal cord tissue. We then summarize potential SCI therapeutic modalities including: (i) hydrogels alone; (ii) hydrogels as cellular or (iii) bioactive molecule delivery vehicles, and; (iv) combinatorial approaches. By linking the structural properties of hydrogels to their functions in treatment with particular focus on immunopharmacological stimuli, this may accelerate further development of functional hydrogels for SCI, and indeed next-generation central nervous system regenerative therapies.

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Abbreviations: BBB, Basso, Beattie and Bresnahan scale; BDNF, brain-derived neurotrophic factor; BMS, Basso mouse scale; BSCB, blood spinal cord barrier; CNS, central nervous system; DRG, dorsal root ganglion; DPI, days post injury; ECM, extracellular matrix; ESC, embryonic stem cell; FGF, fibroblast growth factor; GelMA, gelatin methacrylate; HA, hyaluronic acid; hUC, human umbilical cord; iNOS, inducible nitric oxide synthase; iPSC, induced pluripotent stem cell; MC, methylcellulose; MSC, mesenchymal stem cell; NPC, neural progenitor cell; NSC, neural stem cell; OEC, olfactory ensheathing cell; PEG, poly(ethylene glycol); PLGA, poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid); RGD, arginine-glycine-aspartic acid; SAP, self-assembling peptide; SDF-1, stromal-derived factor 1; SCI, spinal cord injury.

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1. Introduction

Traumatic spinal cord injury (SCI) is a complex medical condition most often caused by motor vehicle accidents or falls (Kang et al., 2018). While there are no exact figures for global prevalence, incidence rates are estimated to vary from 13 to 220 new cases per million people each year (Kang et al., 2018). SCI diminishes quality of life and leads to severe impairment due to motor, sensory and autonomic deficits following irreversible damage to the spinal cord tissue. Despite major advances in pharmacological and surgical treatment approaches (Rabchevsky, Patel, & Springer, 2011; Tohda & Kuboyama, 2011), there is still no curative therapy currently available for SCI patients, and hence the individual and broader socio-economic impacts of this condition are devastating.

1.1. Overview of SCI pathology

Understanding the pathophysiological events of the distinct injury phases in SCI and the resulting limited functional recovery is critical for designing successful treatment strategies. The initial mechanical damage to the spinal cord results in the 'primary injury' phase which can last for up to 24 h and is associated with the death of neural and glial cells (Silva, Sousa, Reis, & Salgado, 2014). Although the primary injury is restricted to the site of insult, it triggers a cascade of biological events that are collectively termed the 'secondary injury'. This stage, which can persist for months and results in damage propagating away from the primary site, is therapeutically targetable. Events of the secondary injury phase include breakdown of the blood spinal cord barrier (BSCB), influx of peripheral inflammatory cells and activation of endogenous microglia, hemorrhagic necrosis, ischemia, free radical species formation, lipid peroxidation, and glutamate excitotoxicity (Silva et al., 2014). The production of inflammatory cytokines by activated macrophages and the presence of serum components due to the compromised BSCB induce the formation of a fibrous glial scar by hypertrophic reactive astrocytes, which surrounds a fluid-filled cystic cavity known as the SCI lesion (O'Shea, Burda, & Sofroniew, 2017; Silver & Miller, 2004). Reactive astrocytes deposit proteoglycans, mainly chondroitin sulphate proteoglycans (CSPGs), in the vicinity of glial scar which impede axonal regeneration (Silver & Miller, 2004). Meanwhile, destruction of oligodendrocytes and demyelination of neural cells due to secondary damage results in the accumulation of myelin debris and myelin associated inhibitors in the primary injury zone. These physical and chemical barriers inhibit axonal regeneration and the reestablishment of damaged neural circuits across the lesion site.

The inflammatory response during the secondary injury phase significantly affects functional and histopathological recovery after SCI. The role of neuroinflammation after SCI is complex and largely depends on the activation state of the immune cells present at the injury site (Rust & Kaiser, 2017). Microglia and macrophages are two such types of cells which dominate the pathological environment following SCI. Simplistically, microglia and macrophages lie on a dynamic spectrum of activation that varies from a classically activated pro-inflammatory state (M1) to an alternatively activated anti-inflammatory state (M2) (Rust & Kaiser, 2017). M1 cells contribute to secondary tissue damage, thus driving alternative activation of macrophages is a promising immunomodulatory strategy. Such approaches have shown therapeutic efficacy in preclinical studies by creating a permissive growth environment to promote tissue healing (Dooley et al., 2016; Guerrero et al., 2012; Ma et al., 2015). However, a translational gap exists as there is no effective treatment currently in use in humans. Current treatment options for SCI focus on pain management and prevention of further damage rather than restoration of lost function through regeneration of damaged tissue (Cox, Varma, & Banik, 2015). Systemic delivery of immunomodulatory biologics, small molecule pro-regenerative drugs or cellular therapeutics poses many challenges such as poor localization and low bioavailability due to BSCB impermeability, necessitating high

therapeutic doses and unwanted side effects (Gerndt et al., 1997; Upadhyay, 2014).

1.2. Can hydrogels transform SCI therapy?

Biomaterials are emerging as an effective method to bridge the translational gap by addressing the complex challenges associated with SCI treatment. In particular, hydrogels are increasingly being used to promote tissue repair and act as vehicles for local therapeutic delivery (of cells or bioactive molecules) in preclinical SCI studies (Fig. 1). Hydrogels are three dimensional (3D) physically entangled and/or chemically cross-linked polymeric structures with high water content that can mimic natural human tissue due to their resemblance to extracellular matrix (ECM) (Brown & Anseth, 2017; Tibbitt & Anseth, 2009). Both natural and synthetic materials can be used as network formers for functional hydrogels for SCI (Zhong & Bellamkonda, 2008). As recently discussed by Cao and co-workers, the exact choice of primary biopolymer(s) and fabrication conditions is key to designing functional hydrogels with tissue biocompatibility, low immunogenicity, and tunable biodegradability (Cao, Wu, Mu, Feng, & Gao, 2021). Hydrogels are a platform from which state-of-the-art treatment strategies for SCI can be developed, as they have possibilities for modifiable physicochemical properties and structural heterogeneity, e.g., aligned architecture to support oriented linear axonal regrowth (Fig. 1). One can then incorporate appropriate biochemical cues to mimic endogenous central nervous system (CNS) tissue to promote a favorable environment for axonal regeneration and activation of regenerative signaling pathways.

Several recent publications have focused on different aspects of the use of biomaterials and scaffolds, including hydrogels, in SCI and CNS repair (Ashammakhi et al., 2019; Ghane, Beigi, Labbaf, Nasr-Esfahani, & Kiani, 2020; Kárová et al., 2020; Macaya & Spector, 2012; Perale et al., 2011). The most recent review by Ghane et al. summarized the design and characterization of commonly applied biomaterials, including hydrogels, for SCI (Ghane, Beigi, Labbaf, Nasr-Esfahani, & Kiani, 2020). Ashammakhi et al. focused on summarizing regenerative therapies, mainly describing biomaterials with pharmacologic agents or cells for SCI repair and providing translational perspectives (Ashammakhi et al., 2019). Multiple additive manufacturing techniques for producing patterned biomaterials for SCI applications were also recently reviewed (Bedir, Ulag, Ustundag and Gunduz, 2020). Since the development and fabrication aspects of such functional materials have been previously summarized (Ashammakhi et al., 2019; Bedir et al., 2020; Cao, Wu, Mu, Feng, & Gao, 2021; Ghane, Beigi, Labbaf, Nasr-Esfahani, & Kiani, 2020; Kárová et al., 2020; Macaya & Spector, 2012; Perale et al., 2011), we will not focus on these details in this review. However, these recent analyses do not evaluate reported links between physicochemical properties of the hydrogel and their primary function (e.g. ability to successfully deliver cells or molecular cargo) or their immunopharmacological outcomes, which is main topic of this review.

The analysis presented here aims to support active consideration of hydrogel characteristics and their relevance to immunomodulatory cues in designing next-generation functional hydrogels for SCI treatment. We will first summarize the most relevant physicochemical properties of functional hydrogels for SCI, addressing how they can be optimized to meet specific immune-therapeutic requirements. We will then discuss the emerging therapeutic use of functional hydrogels in cell therapy as well as bioactive molecule delivery for SCI, in particular highlighting the potential for immunomodulation. Finally, based on all presented findings, recommendations for designing a hydrogel-based therapy for SCI are proposed. This may facilitate inclusion of steps to modulate the complex secondary inflammatory response into bio-materials design for SCI and provide a next step towards successful therapeutic and translational materials choices.

Fig. 1. Overview of SCI pathophysiology and the current therapeutic applications of hydrogels for SCI. Hydrogels can be used as delivery vehicles for cells or bioactive molecules and can provide physical support to regenerating tissue. Figure created with [Biorender.com](https://www.biorender.com).

2. Physicochemical properties required to develop functional hydrogels for immunopharmacological interventions after SCI

Here, we summarize important physicochemical characteristics of functional hydrogels (mechanical properties; topography and porosity; surface charge; structural heterogeneity, and; suitability for carrying appropriate bio-chemical cues) which are key in developing functional and immunomodulatory materials for SCI treatment. We will then demonstrate how the integration of biomolecules, cell types, or fillers into hydrogels can produce functional nanocomposite hydrogel matrices that retain their underlying characteristics (high permeability, cell compatibility, printability *etc.*), which can be further manipulated *in situ* to induce regeneration of living tissue post SCI.

2.1. Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of spinal cord tissue depend on the anatomical origin. Typical measurements do not resolve spatial tissue anisotropies, which have also been observed in the cervical spinal cord. In fact, local cell distribution and axonal orientation determine spinal cord biomechanics (Koser, Moendarbary, Hanne, Kuerten, & Franze, 2015). Complete spatial elasticity maps were obtained using atomic force indentation *ex vivo* at a resolution of 50 μm , covering almost complete spinal cord cross-sections of tissue harvested after cervical dislocation. Whilst overall spinal cord bulk properties remain in the 5–20 kPa range, localized tissue mechanics measurements can

reflect softer components of 70–130 Pa in the white and gray matter (Koser et al., 2015). On the other hand, mechanical properties of fresh spinal cord tissue from Sprague-Dawley rats (Fig. 2A) were measured using dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) and compared to clinically graded hydrogels (Fig. 2B) (Bartlett et al., 2020). Clinical-grade collagen, fibrin and alginate hydrogels (Fig. 2B) (Bartlett et al., 2020), as well as multiple other clinical candidates (Wang, Chung, Pui-Yik Chan, & Kurisawa, 2010), are emerging as options for spinal cord tissue replacement due to their tunable mechanical properties. Spatial control over necessary stiffness heterogeneity (in the optimal 5–20 kPa range with local stiffness heterogeneity down to 70 Pa (Koser et al., 2015)) can be achieved by various fabrication and patterning methods that can begin to mimic the spatially heterogeneous biomechanics of CNS tissue, which will be described below. Prager and co-workers recently summarized the clinical target stiffness of hydrogels using non-invasive ultrasound elastography (as benchmarked against standard indentation on phantom polyacrylamide hydrogels) (Prager et al., 2020). Their recorded values lay in the stiffness range of the 5–40 kPa, thus giving overall indications of the upper clinically relevant limit of target stiffness for successful *in vivo* hydrogel implants. We note that although stiffness is an important factor driving tissue regeneration post SCI, as long as the construct physically supports the surrounding tissue, other factors appear more important, as will be described below. In optimal therapies, compromise between physical stiffness, porosity, topography, and the ability to deliver cells or molecules will have to be achieved.

Fig. 2. (A) Comparison of compound modulus values for different sections of the spinal cord; (B) Mechanical benchmarking of collagen and fibrin hydrogels against cervical spinal cord compound modulus; Means \pm SEM. (A–B) are adapted with permission from (Bartlett, Eleftheriadou, Evans, Choi, & Phillips, 2020). Copyright © 2020 Elsevier. (C–H) Characteristics of GelMA hydrogels. (C1–C3) Representative scanning electron microscope images of the surfaces of the three hydrogel systems. (D) Quantification of the average pore sizes of the GelMA hydrogels (* and ** indicate $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$, respectively). (E) Representative stress–strain curves of three hydrogel samples. (F) Young's modulus significantly decreases with hydrogel softness (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$). (G) Appearance of the GelMA hydrogel. (H) Mouse spinal cord can adhere to GelMA hydrogels *in vitro*. (C–H) are adapted with permission from Fan et al. (2018). Copyright © 2018 American Chemical Society.

2.2. Topography and porosity

Hydrogels are of particular interest for tissue engineering applications due to their wide (and tunable) porosity range which permits transport of entities of widely varying size; *i.e.* enabling cell migration and diffusion of nutrients and other relevant factors, facilitating cell signaling and angiogenesis, and maintaining oxygenation (Derkus et al., 2020; Kourgiantaki et al., 2020). One factor to consider when designing hydrogels with a porous structure is the size of cells required to infiltrate the scaffold, which ranges from astrocytes (average $c.140 \mu\text{m}$ diameter) down to oligodendrocytes ($6\text{--}9 \mu\text{m}$) (Edgar & Griffiths, 2009; Oberheim et al., 2009). Therefore, one must take into account the extended size distribution requirements, possibly targeting porosity

from 2 to $250 \mu\text{m}$, reflecting the cells comprising spinal cord tissue. Indeed, pore size distributions ranging from 22 to $200 \mu\text{m}$ have been reported to successfully allow penetration of nerve fibers, which themselves have diameters in the range from 0.3 to $20 \mu\text{m}$ (Saliani et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2019). Recently, Ma et al. reported a hydrogel formed from gelatin methacrylate (GelMA), with a pore size distribution in the required range for infiltration of activated microglia/macrophages (Ma et al., 2020). Fan and co-workers also designed distinct GelMA hydrogels for SCI repair with varied porosity (Fig. 2C–D) that correlated well to the mechanical properties of the resulting hydrogels (Fig. 2E–F) (Fan et al., 2018). Both recorded porosity and compressive modulus of the three GelMA hydrogels matched the requirements of the original spinal cord tissue. Fan and co-workers also demonstrated

the natural ability of GelMA hydrogels to adhere to the rat's spinal cord (Fig. 2G–H).

It is worth highlighting the challenges with imaging and indeed quantifying true 3D porosity/pore size distribution using microscopic methods, as these require destructive preparations and data reconstruction. The typical approach involves lyophilizing/freeze drying hydrogels (thus amending true porosity structure), post-coating with conductive thin layers (e.g. 10 nm) and imaging using electron or cryo-electron microscopies (Grenier et al., 2019; Leal-Egaña, Braumann, Díaz-Cuenca, Nowicki, & Bader, 2011; Wychowaniec, Litowczenko, et al., 2020), whereas non-destructive, more precise methods include small angle x-ray scattering (Wisotzki, Tempesti, Fratini, & Mayr, 2017). That being said, porosity is one of the most critical hydrogel characteristics for successful spinal cord tissue regrowth and repair. More detailed analysis of pore structure over implant lifetime may prove instructive.

2.3. Surface charge

Hydrogels are often described as 'negatively-' or 'positively-charged', referring to the overall charge on the network polymer at a given (typically physiological) pH. Surface charges on (bio)polymers arise from acid-base ionization (e.g. $-\text{COOH} \leftrightarrow -\text{COO}^- + \text{H}^+$, $-\text{NH}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \leftrightarrow -\text{NH}_3^+ + \text{OH}^-$) and are driven by the environment pH and ion balance (Wychowaniec, Smith, et al., 2020). A pioneering study published in 2014 investigated how ionization in nanocomposite films (which included 'positive' amine-grafted graphene oxide into polyethyleneimine) affected neural cell development. Positively-charged matrices were shown to be more beneficial for neurite outgrowth and branching (Tu et al., 2014). These observations are consistent with results from previous studies (Dadsetan, Knight, Lu, Windebank, & Yaszemski, 2009; Hejčl et al., 2009) which demonstrated that surface modifications of hydrogels with monomers that bear a positive-charge improved primary sensory neuron surface adhesion and differentiation in rats. Enhanced adhesion of dorsal root ganglion (DRG) explants containing sensory neurons, Schwann cells (SCs) and neuronal support cells have also been described for positively-charged hydrogels.

On the other hand, successful outcomes were also achieved using human embryonic stem cell-derived neural stem cells cultured on negatively-charged hydrogels based on e.g. hyaluronic acid (HA) (Zarei-Kheirabadi et al., 2020). Hejčl and co-workers investigated the effect of differently charged (positive or negative) hydrogels on the regeneration of multiple cell types using 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA) implanted into rat spinal cord hemisection cavities (Hejčl et al., 2009). It was reported that positively or negatively-charged functional groups promoted axonal regeneration inside the implant, while minimal infiltration of axons into the hydrogels occurred in the absence of charged chemical functionalities, suggesting charge is a guiding cue for axonal growth (Hejčl et al., 2009). Interestingly, only hydrogels with positively-charged functional groups demonstrated improved axonal regeneration into the center of the implant, in line with the preponderance of studies linking axonal regeneration to positive charge (Dadsetan et al., 2009; Hejčl et al., 2009; Tu et al., 2014). Similarly, the best connective tissue ingrowth was observed for positively-charged hydrogels (Hejčl et al., 2009). Hence, successful tissue regeneration is often associated with positively charged hydrogels. However, surprisingly, astrocytes infiltrated only hydrogel implants with a negative or neutral charge, and were mostly found in the peripheral zones (Hejčl et al., 2009) suggesting a more nuanced response.

Overall, most recent literature suggests that charge influences different cell types differently, hence it may not be possible to optimize supports using charge alone. In time, spatial patterning of charged cues may be realized to direct growth through oriented architectures, just as patterning of chemical cues for directing cellular processes is already realized (Fisher et al., 2018; Li et al., 2021; Vega et al., 2018). For now, the best pragmatic approach may be optimizing other factors key to SCI repair, such as the type of cells delivered. Finally, we note that surface

charge will impact the mechanisms of delivery of charged molecules and therapeutics (including immunomodulatory substances), which will be further discussed below.

2.4. On the importance of alignment

Designing the inner fibrous matrix of hydrogels to achieve anisotropic and aligned pore/fiber architecture has been shown to offer physical guidance cues for directional axon growth (McMurtrey, 2014; Saglam et al., 2013; Winter et al., 2016). Furthermore, channels within hydrogel matrices can facilitate angiogenesis which is essential for axonal regeneration (Li et al., 2021). However, unlike axon growth, formation of new blood vessels does not need to occur with defined directionality but rather should provide sufficient oxygen and nutrient perfusion throughout the regenerated tissue. Typically, channel sizes of 250 μm are used, which are comparable to axonal white matter tract sizes in spinal cord (Cao, Wu, Mu, Feng, & Gao, 2021). On the other hand, oversized channels or pores may negatively influence the cellular adhesion and infiltration, impairing neural outgrowth, and possibly compromising the long-term mechanical integrity of hydrogel implants (Chen et al., 2018; Dumont et al., 2019; Gros, Sakamoto, Blesch, Havton, & Tuszynski, 2010; Li et al., 2016). A range of fabrication methods and tools can support the formation of structured and aligned scaffolds (Ghane, Beigi, Labbaf, Nasr-Esfahani, & Kiani, 2020). There have been interesting reports of; electrospinning of hydrogels (Chen et al., 2019; McMurtrey, 2014; Nguyen et al., 2017; Yao et al., 2018); 3D bioprinting (Bedir et al., 2020), and; addition of responsive fillers, e.g. magnetic nanoparticles (Antman-Passig & Shefi, 2016) or conductive carbon nanotubes (CNTs) (Seven et al., 2020) which align on application of magnetic and electric fields, respectively. These methods for inducing alignment of polymer fibers that persist across nano- to micro- length scales (from 3 nm up to 500 μm) can provide necessary directional physical guidance for axons. Other methods rely on carefully controlled photochemistry processes. For example, McKinnon et al. designed a photodegradable hydrogel from poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) cross-linked through a strain promoted alkyne–azide cycloaddition (McKinnon, Brown, Kyburz, Kiyotake, & Anseth, 2014). After the hydrogels were formed, a 2-photon infrared approach was used to induce spatially controlled degradation paths through cleavage of a nitrobenzyl ether moiety, effectively cutting user-defined high-precision channels through the gels 3D structure. The authors cut channel widths of 2, 5, 20 and 50 μm and observed no statistically significant differences in axonal regrowth down to 2 μm , thus setting a possible lower limit of $\approx 5 \mu\text{m}$ for useful channel dimensions in SCI repair.

Often, shear, e.g. arising from injection during implantation *in vivo*, can induce nanofibre alignment (Wychowaniec, Smith, et al., 2020). 3D printing technology can also be used to construct printed hydrogel implants with selected orientation of individual fibrils, such as in the case of Schwab et al. (Schwab, Hélarý, et al., 2020). We will describe such approaches in the next section.

2.5. Towards heterogeneous and hierarchical structures

Technical developments in 3D printing methodologies and associated bio-inks (hydrogels) currently allow for high-precision recapitulation of complex tissues (Fonseca et al., 2020; Schwab, Levato, et al., 2020). Juang et al. bio-printed (extrusion-based) a multichannel scaffold with neuronal and glial progenitor cells evaluating multiple bio-ink candidates in the process (Fig. 3A–F) (Joung et al., 2018). Heterogeneity was achieved both through printing parallel aligned hydrogel lines, and by positioning clusters of induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived NPCs and oligodendrocyte progenitor cells at selected locations within the 3D construct at 200 μm center-to-center separation (Fig. 3B). This approach also demonstrates the possibility of forming aligned channels for physical guidance, as mentioned in the previous section. Rapid NPC differentiation and axon extension observed

throughout (150 μm wide) channels showcase the potential for architectural control of cell behavior. Finally, the resulting scaffold enhanced cell-cell communication, as confirmed by the observation of spontaneous physiological calcium flux across the printed implant. A similar approach was recently confirmed by Wang and co-workers who spatially positioned bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) and rat SCs to promote the formation of intercellular connections and cell-directed differentiation for over 28 days (Wang, Wang, et al., 2021).

In another study, Koffler *et al.* developed a continuous microscale stereolithographic projection method to print an NPC-loaded (GelMA and PEG diacrylate) hydrogel of a section of rodent spinal cord to fill the rostral to caudal region (Koffler et al., 2019). The implant was built with microchannels in the 200 μm width range, which were positioned to mimic the area of axonal tracts in the surrounding white matter. To enhance structural integrity, a replica of gray matter area was fully

printed as solid hydrogel matrix. The authors found that severed axons regenerated across the native/synthetic boundary and synapsed with implanted NPCs in the implant *in vivo*. At 4 weeks following implantation, extended axons were observed growing out of the hydrogel into the rodent spinal cord below the injury site, apparently improving both synaptic transmission and functional outcome significantly (Koffler et al., 2019). Stereolithography can also be used to print scaffolds with biochemical gradients, e.g. growth factors, such as those described by Cui *et al.* (Li et al., 2021) (Fig. 3G–I). In their approach, Cui and co-workers printed various hydrogel scaffolds (polyethylene glycol diacrylate, GelMA, and methacrylated HA) with parallel channels of 400 or 800 μm width (exemplar 400 μm is shown in Fig. 3I). Furthermore, a high-low concentration gradient of SDF-1 was patterned in the scaffolds from one channel end to the other (Fig. 3I). In this study, SDF-1 did not significantly induce cell migration from NSC spheroids compared to the

Fig. 3. Additive manufacturing approaches for generating functional spinal cord tissue scaffolds. (A) A scheme of the spinal cord depicting gray and white matter boundaries with an accompanying model of a 3D bioprinted multichannel scaffold (B) Representation of the 3D bioprinting process. Selected bioinks are printed at specific temperatures, of 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ or 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to allow temperature transition of the inks and appropriate structural support, in a layer-by-layer process. (C) Side-by-side visualization of a transected rat spinal cord and the printed functional (amendable) multichannel hydrogel scaffold. (D) Printing resolution of ≈ 150 μm was achieved as demonstrated in the top view image of the printed scaffold. (E) Side view image of a 5 mm long printed scaffold. (F) The scale ($2 \times 2 \times 5$ mm^3) of printed scaffold is demonstrated. (A–F) adapted with permission from (Joung et al., 2018). Copyright © 2018, John Wiley & Sons, Inc. (G–I) 3D printed scaffolds with controlled distribution of stromal-derived factor 1 (SDF-1) guided cell migration. (G) Schematic of 3D printed growth factor gradient. (H) Scaffold design. (I) FITC (green) loaded in the hydrogel scaffold with a gradient concentration. Scale bar: 200 μm . (G–I) Adapted with permission from (Li et al., 2021). Copyright © 2021, American Chemical Society.

non-gradient case, indicating that topography alone was a sufficient factor for influencing cellular behavior. Nevertheless, this approach demonstrated the ability to pattern biochemical cues that may be useful in SCI studies.

We note that increasingly adaptable and internally-ordered hydrogel constructs are currently under development. These approaches better mimic native heterogeneous architecture, mechanics and charge, and are designed to be appropriately degradable, to provide opportunity for SCI repair and improved functional outcome (Higuchi et al., 2019; Hlavac, Kasper, & Schmidt, 2020). In this section we noted the most important and optimal hydrogel physicochemical properties, which will be further discussed in Section 3 in the context of their immunopharmacological interventions for SCI.

3. Immunopharmacological applications of hydrogels for SCI

As mentioned above, the general design considerations and therapeutic strategies applied for a broad range of functional scaffolds for SCI have been previously summarized (Cao, Wu, Mu, Feng, & Gao, 2021). In the next sections we will provide an overview of the potential therapeutic use of hydrogels by focusing on their ability to deliver specific immunopharmacological agents and thereby modulate the inflammatory response after SCI. In particular, we describe their use as delivery vehicles of cells or bioactive molecules with immunomodulatory properties, and as components of combinatorial therapies.

The secondary inflammatory response after SCI has long been recognized as a dual-edged sword that can either promote recovery or exacerbate damage, depending on the activation state of the immune cells present at the injury site (Rust & Kaiser, 2017; Vidal, Lemmens, Dooley, & Hendrix, 2013). The preclinical SCI landscape has seen a shift towards the use of immunomodulatory therapies that drive a stronger M2 macrophage (anti-inflammatory) response after injury (Al Mamun et al., 2021; Monteiro, Salgado, & Silva, 2018). Since hydrogels can retain their porous structure in an aqueous environment, they may be used as delivery vehicles (e.g. for drugs, growth factors or cells) which can be locally applied for spatially defined release with potential for programmed delay or even responsive temporal control.

3.1. Inherent immunomodulatory properties of hydrogels

While most hydrogel-based therapies for SCI exploit the delivery capacity of the hydrogel, some studies have shown that certain hydrogels have inherent immunomodulatory properties capable of reducing the damaging inflammatory response in SCI models *in vitro* and *in vivo*. For example, Rayahin and colleagues showed that high molecular weight (>1000 kDa) HA can polarize macrophages to an M2 phenotype, whereas low molecular weight HA drives pro-inflammatory M1 polarization (Rayahin, Buhrman, Zhang, Koh, & Gemeinhart, 2015). In Table 1, we present a complete list of studies that provide evidence for inherent immunomodulatory properties of hydrogels in preclinical SCI studies, selected examples of which are discussed in the text. This approach will be adopted throughout this review. We specifically note the original hydrogel precursor and any physical or chemical modification made to the hydrogel, the *in vitro/in vivo* models used and the application strategy, as well as the functional (i.e. BBB/BMS score systems (Basso et al., 2006; Basso, Beattie, Fau-Bresnahan, & Bresnahan, 1995)) and histopathological outcomes observed.

HA, for example, is one of the main components of the extracellular matrix and is widely used for hydrogel synthesis in SCI. HA is the principal ligand of the transmembrane receptor CD44 present on all cells, including immune cells. High molecular weight HA (with Mw ~1000 kDa can bind to multiple CD44 receptors across a larger cell surface (Rayahin et al., 2015) and in doing so can prevent the activation of NF- κ B signaling and suppress pro-inflammatory cytokine production compared to low molecular weight HA (Altman et al., 2019; Noble, McKee, Cowman, & Shin, 1996). Schizas et al. demonstrated that murine

organotypic spinal cord slice cultures grown on HA-based (with 360 kDa molecular weight of HA) hydrogels showed a significant reduction in the number of activated microglia compared to slices grown on polyethylene terephthalate membranes (Schizas et al., 2014). Austin et al. injected a HA/methylcellulose (HAMC) hydrogel into the intrathecal space of a rat clip compression SCI model with post-traumatic syringomyelia (Austin et al., 2012). They found that hydrogel treatment led to a modest reduction in microglia/macrophage numbers and the pro-inflammatory response, demonstrated by a reduction in Iba-1 staining in the meninges and reduced IL-1 β expression, as well as a significant improvement in BBB scores. Han et al. synthesized an anti-inflammatory hydrogel by immersing a HA hydrogel in tauroursodeoxycholic acid (TUDCA) and subsequently injected it into a rat contusion model (Han et al., 2020). The treatment significantly reduced expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β , IFN- γ , IL-6 and TNF- α , and improved BBB scores.

Decellularized ECM can also be used to prepare hydrogels that contain HA, collagen, laminin, and fibronectin to accurately mimic the native ECM environment. These hydrogels have successfully been prepared from porcine brain, spinal cord, urinary bladder, and hUC (Kočí et al., 2017). ECM hydrogels promote MSC migration *in vitro*, and ~77% of macrophages that infiltrated the hydrogel after injection into a focal ischemic lesion in the rat motor cortex were CD206⁺ M2 macrophages (Kočí et al., 2017). Tukmachev et al. tested this system in a rat hemisection model and found that CD86⁺ M1 macrophages surrounded the hydrogel while CD206⁺ M2 macrophages were present within the hydrogel itself (Tukmachev et al., 2016). No functional analysis was performed, however axonal ingrowth was significantly improved (Tukmachev et al., 2016).

Synthetic hydrogels have also been used for SCI, for instance Hong et al. designed a novel hydrogel from imidazole-poly (organophosphazenes) that physically interacts with histamine receptors on endogenous macrophages to induce the expression of matrix metalloproteinase-9 in these cells and subsequent macrophage-mediated ECM remodeling (Hong et al., 2017). The imidazole-poly (organophosphazenes) hydrogel with MW of 14–18 kDa was amphiphilic and shear-thinning, allowing rapid sol-gel transition from 4 to 37 °C upon *in vivo* injection. This led to elimination of cystic cavities in a rat contusion model due to the production of a fibrotic ECM that was densely populated by macrophages, many of which were CD206⁺ M2 macrophages retained at the injury site due to physical interactions with the hydrogel. The significantly improved BBB scores in the hydrogel-treated group indicate that synthetic hydrogels can be designed to target macrophages to improve functional recovery after SCI. Despite this reported success of synthetic materials, the natural origin, extensive literature base, and established therapeutic efficacy of HA in the treatment of multiple inflammatory conditions (e.g. osteoarthritis (Altman et al., 2019)) have resulted in it becoming a common choice for immunomodulatory approaches.

Overall, studies presented in Table 1 show the importance of selecting an appropriate starting material for hydrogel synthesis as they differ in capacity to modulate the immune response. Natural materials that mimic the native ECM can promote M2 cell migration into the hydrogel, while synthetic materials offer a more reproducible platform from a translational perspective. However, as we discuss in further sections, immunomodulatory properties of hydrogels can be further improved by the inclusion of cells or bioactive molecules.

3.2. Hydrogels as effective cell delivery vehicles

Current cell-based SCI therapies include replacing damaged neural cells, aiding in remyelination, and releasing neurotrophic factors through transplantation of different cell types including neural stem cells (NSCs), MSCs, SCs, olfactory ensheathing cells (OECs), embryonic stem cells (ESCs) and iPSCs into the injury site (Kubínová & Syková, 2012). However, transplanted cells face many barriers upon

Table 1

Applications of hydrogels to support tissue remodeling after SCI. BBB/BMS: Basso, Beattie and Bresnahan / Basso Mouse Scale describe two gold standard locomotor rating scales used to assess functional recovery in preclinical rat and mouse models of SCI, respectively.

Gel	Modifications	Experimental model of SCI		Therapeutic Strategy	Observations		Ref
		<i>In vitro</i>	<i>In vivo</i>		Functional	Histopathological	
Decellularized ECM	–	Human umbilical cord (hUC)-MSCs and rat DRGs	Rat hemisection model	Comparison of spinal cord (SC)- derived and urinary bladder (UB)- derived ECM hydrogels via injection at T8 level immediately after injury.	No functional analysis.	Addition of hMSCs to the hydrogel did not further improve axon or blood vessel ingrowth in SC-derived gels. M2 macrophage present within the gel. No difference between SC- and UB-derived hydrogels.	(Tukmachev et al., 2016)
Gelatin	–	RAW 264.7 macrophage cell line and primary rat bone marrow-derived (B)MSCs	–	Growth of macrophages on nanofibrous and smooth gelatin matrices to assess the effect of nanofibrous architecture on macrophages. Treatment of macrophages <i>in vitro</i> with HA of varying molecular weights (5–3000 kDa).	No functional analysis.	No difference in secretion of inflammatory cytokines between groups. Nanofibrous architecture and coculture with BMSCs reduced expression of <i>nos2</i> and prevented downregulation of <i>Mrc1</i> . Low molecular weight HA induces M1 phenotype - increased expression of <i>nos2</i> , <i>tnf</i> , <i>il12b</i> , and <i>cd80</i> ; increased secretion of nitric oxide and TNF- α . High molecular weight HA promotes M2 phenotype – increased expression of <i>arg1</i> , <i>il10</i> , and <i>mrc1</i> ; enhanced arginase activity.	(Wu, Ma, Liang, Chen, & Liu, 2020)
Hyaluronic acid (HA)	–	Murine J774A.1 macrophage cell line	–	Growth of OSCSCs on HA-based hydrogel for four days.	No functional analysis.	Increased number of neurons throughout the spinal cord slice. Increased number of astrocytes and resting microglia in white matter. Decreased number of activated microglia in gray matter.	(Rayahin et al., 2015)
	–	Mouse organotypic spinal cord slice cultures (OSCSCs)	–	Growth of OSCSCs on HA-based hydrogel for four days.	No functional analysis.	Increased number of neurons throughout the spinal cord slice. Increased number of astrocytes and resting microglia in white matter. Decreased number of activated microglia in gray matter.	(Schizas et al., 2014)
	HA modified with methylcellulose (MC) at 1:3 HA:MC; poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) nanoparticles at 10 wt%	–	Rat clip compression model	Intrathecal injection of hydrogel at the T2 level immediately after injury.	No significant difference in BBB scores.	No change in lesion size, astrogliosis or inflammatory response.	(Baumann, Kang, Tator, & Shoichet, 2010)
	HA modified with glycidyl methacrylate groups	Neonatal and adult primary rat astrocyte culture	Rat dorsal hemisection model	Hydrogel implantation at T8 level immediately after injury.	No functional analysis.	Decreased number of reactive macrophage/microglia and decreased astrocyte reactivity.	(Khaing et al., 2011)
	HA modified with MC to obtain 2% HA and 7% MC solution	–	Rat clip compression model with post-traumatic syringo-myelia	Intrathecal hydrogel injection caudal to injury site 24 h after injury.	Improved BBB scores and axonal inflammation and scarring. No improvement on inclined plane apparatus.	Attenuation of subarachnoid inflammation and scarring. Decreased lesion volume and inflammatory cytokine expression. No change in neutrophil or macrophage/microglial activation.	(Austin et al., 2012)
–	–	Rat hemisection model	Intraparenchymal hydrogel injection at T9 level immediately after injury.	No significant difference in BBB scores.	Reduced lesion volume and scar tissue formation. Improved axon alignment and remyelination. Reduced number of mononuclear cells.	(Sergiy et al., 2016)	
–	Glycol chitosan and oxidized HA gels of 7:3, 8:2, and 9:1 ratios immersed in 1 mM tauroursodeoxycholic acid (TUDCA)	–	Rat contusion model	Intraparenchymal hydrogel injection at the T9 level immediately after injury.	Improved BBB scores.	Reduced secretion of IL-1 β , IFN- γ , IL-6 and TNF- α compared to controls. Inhibition of the inflammatory MAPK pathway.	(Han et al., 2020)
Synthetic	Imidazole-poly (organophosphazenes) hydrogel	Mouse NIH3T3 fibroblast and RAW 264.7 macrophage cell lines	Rat contusion model	Intraparenchymal hydrogel injection at T10 level one week after injury.	Improved BBB scores. No improvement in base of support or the angle of hindpaw rotation.	Activation of macrophage-mediated wound healing responses and fibrotic ECM remodeling. No cystic cavities.	(Hong et al., 2017)

Table 1 (continued)

Gel	Modifications	Experimental model of SCI		Therapeutic Strategy	Observations		Ref
		<i>In vitro</i>	<i>In vivo</i>		Functional	Histopathological	
Synthetic	Methacrylate hydrogels: hydroxypropylmethacrylamid (HPMA), 2-hydroxyethylmethacrylate (HEMA) and a HEMA hydrogel with fibronectin (HEMA-Fn)	–	Rat hemisection model	–	No significant difference in BBB scores. Some improvement in plantar test scores in HEMA-Fn and HPMA groups at week 5 and week 12 post injury, respectively.	Preservation of motor neurons and myelinated tissue. Decreased macrophage/microglia staining intensity. Presence of M2 macrophages. Connective tissue ingrowth and axonal regeneration in HPMA. No significant increase in genes relating to regeneration, astrogliosis or macrophage infiltration.	(Hejčl et al., 2018)

implantation such as the presence of growth inhibitory factors, pro-inflammatory cytokines, cellular debris, and an ischemic environment (Assunção-Silva, Gomes, Sousa, Silva, & Salgado, 2015; Dooley, Vidal, & Hendrix, 2014; Kubinova & Syková, 2012). Low cell viability, cellular de-differentiation and poor localization of cells to the injury site currently limit clinical application of cell-based therapies.

Hydrogels are currently being designed to overcome these limitations by modulating the inhibitory environment and allowing delivery of cells directly to the injury site. Table 2 collates recent examples of pre-clinical SCI studies that apply hydrogel-based strategies for cell delivery with reported effects on the secondary inflammatory response after injury.

Hydrogels derived from natural materials are again a common choice for enhancing the survival of transplanted cells, with cell adhesive peptides, e.g. RGD peptide (Gomes et al., 2016) and laminin-derived peptides (Li et al., 2020) also playing a beneficial role in improving the localization of cell grafts to the injury site. MSCs are particularly interesting from an immunomodulatory perspective, and their therapeutic potential in SCI is discussed further below along with how they can be combined with other cell types within a hydrogel to further promote functional recovery after injury. In the following subsections, we will refer to and discuss the studies presented in Table 2.

3.2.1. Hydrogels for MSC delivery

The immunomodulatory properties of MSCs are well recognized in the treatment of inflammatory conditions due to their production of soluble factors (e.g. TNF- β 1, IL-13, neurotrophin-3 (NT-3), IL-10, IL-6, ciliary neurotrophic factor (CNTF) (Sobacchi, Palagano, Villa, & Menale, 2017)) for paracrine signaling that can control inflammation and limit damage to surrounding tissue; this is often referred to as the 'bystander effect' (Liau et al., 2020). Engraftment of MSCs alone has been used in clinical trials for SCI, however poor graft cell survival necessitates multiple administrations, which is a significant disadvantage for clinical translation (Liau et al., 2020).

Hydrogels fabricated from natural materials enhance cell viability by providing a physical support for transplanted cells that mimics the native ECM due to cell adhesive properties. Natural hydrogels (e.g. chitosan, gelatin, agarose) have been shown to provide a suitable platform for MSC graft survival in preclinical SCI studies (Boido et al., 2019; Caron et al., 2016; Yao et al., 2021). Furthermore, incorporation of bioactive ECM motifs into the hydrogel enhances MSC viability and maintains

stemness, which supports ongoing MSC-driven release of neuroprotective and immunomodulatory factors including but not limited to brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), β - nerve growth factor and IL-10 (Joyce et al., 2010; Papa et al., 2018). Caron et al. demonstrated in a mouse compression SCI model that the use of an agarose hydrogel loaded with MSCs was capable of polarizing macrophages to a neuro-protective M2 phenotype *via* the gradual release of the CCL2 chemokine nine days post-injury, while injection of MSCs alone or hydrogel alone into the injury site did not have any significant immunomodulatory effect (Caron et al., 2016). Similarly, Boido et al. showed that a chitosan hydrogel was suitable for supporting MSC survival for at least one week *in vivo* and maintaining their ability to secrete vesicles for at least five days *in vitro*, which are essential aspects for delivery of immunomodulatory factors (Boido et al., 2019).

3.2.2. Hydrogels for delivery of other cell types

MSCs may also be used in combination with other cell types in a multi-faceted strategy to modulate the immune microenvironment after SCI and replace damaged cell types. NSCs are commonly used for this purpose; however uncontrolled cellular differentiation poses an inherent limitation to their use. In fact, the hostile microenvironment in the injured spinal cord drives astrocytic differentiation of NSCs which can result in allodynia (Liu et al., 2019; Macias et al., 2006). Hydrogels can counteract this problem by locally controlling differentiation, e.g. by incorporating growth factors within the hydrogel matrix to direct cellular differentiation (Geissler et al., 2018; Li et al., 2016). Alternatively, paracrine factors such as BDNF and NT-3 released by the cells themselves within the hydrogel may also direct NSC differentiation. Zhou et al. demonstrated in a rat hemisection model that the combination of MSCs and NSCs in a GelMA hydrogel promotes neuronal and oligodendrocytic differentiation of NSCs *in vitro*, reduces inflammation and improves functional recovery *in vivo* compared to GelMA-mediated delivery of either cell type alone (Zhou et al., 2020). Kobashi et al. recently demonstrated that injection of Matrigel containing IL-4-stimulated primary M2 microglia into an injured mouse spinal cord resulted in significantly improved BMS scores, increased expression of M2 markers Arg-1 and Mrc1 and decreased expression of M1 markers CD86 and NOS2 four weeks after injury (Kobashi et al., 2020). When compared with systemic injection of IL-4 the cellular transplantation approach showed improved outcomes, demonstrating the advantage of gel-based delivery of therapies directly to the injury site.

Table 2
Applications of hydrogels as cell delivery vehicles for immunomodulatory purposes in SCI.

Gel	Modifications	Experimental model of SCI		Therapeutic Strategy	Observations		Ref
		<i>In vitro</i>	<i>In vivo</i>		Functional	Histopathological	
Agarose	Carbomer:Agarose:PEG in 1:3:1 ratio. Carbomer is functionalized with arginine-glycine-aspartic acid (RGD) peptide, Gels were loaded with hMSCs for ECM deposition.	Human cord blood primary MSCs	Mouse clip compression model	Delivery of hMSCs at the T12 level via hydrogel insertion immediately after injury.	No functional analysis (Caron et al., 2016) Improved BMS scores. (Papa et al., 2018)	ECM deposition improves MSC viability <i>in vitro</i> . Higher number of M2 macrophage at the injury site.	(Caron et al., 2016; Papa et al., 2018)
Chitosan	–	Murine primary BMSCs; SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cell line	Mouse transection model	Delivery of MSCs at the T13 level via hydrogel injection immediately after injury.	No functional analysis.	MSCs remain viable and capable of secreting extracellular vesicles <i>in vitro</i> . MSCs could enter and surround the lesion in the <i>in vivo</i> proof-of-concept. Reduced lesion size.	(Boido et al., 2019)
Gelatin	Gelatin functionalized with methacrylate (GelMA)	Mouse iPSC-derived NPCs	Mouse transection model	Delivery of iNPCs via hydrogel implantation at the T9 level immediately after injury.	Significant improvement in BMS scores and footprint analysis	Increased axonal regeneration. Decreased number of reactive macrophages/microglia.	(Fan et al., 2018)
	GelMA	Primary rat BMSCs and spinal NSCs	Rat hemisection model	Delivery of NSCs and MSCs at the T8 level immediately after injury.	Improved BBB scores.	Reduced lesion volume and number of inflammatory cells. Increased neuronal differentiation and remyelination.	(Zhou et al., 2020)
	Gelatin-hydroxyphenyl with horse radish peroxidase and galactose oxidase for dual enzymatic cross-linking.	Primary hUC-MSCs	Mouse contusion model	Delivery of hUC-MSCs via hydrogel injection at the T10 level immediately after injury.	Significant improvement in BMS scores and footprint analysis	Reduced expression of IL-6, TNF- α and apoptotic markers. Increased neurogenesis.	(Yao et al., 2021)
Gellan gum	Maleimide-modified RGD peptide immobilized to furan-modified gellan gum.	Primary human adipose-derived stem cells (ASCs), rat OECs and rat DRGs	Rat hemisection model	Delivery of ASCs and OECs via hydrogel implantation at the L1 level immediately after injury.	Improved BBB scores and longer distances travelled.	Presence of OECs did not improve neurite extension <i>in vitro</i> . No significant improvement in number of astrocytes or inflammatory cells <i>in vivo</i> .	(Gomes et al., 2016)
HA	HA modified with MC-streptavidin and immobilized biotinylated PGDF-A.	Primary rat NSPCs	Rat clip compression model	Transplantation of NSPCs via direct injection or hydrogel injection at T2 level 9 days post injury (dpi).	Improved fine motor control. No significant difference in BBB scores.	Hydrogel supported cell viability <i>in vitro</i> . Reduced lesion size. Oligodendrocyte and neuronal sparing. No change in inflammatory response.	(Mothe, Tam, Zahir, Tator, & Shoichet, 2013)
	Thiol-modified HA and thiol-modified gelatin mixed in equal volumes.	Human ESC-derived NSCs	Rat contusion model	Delivery of hESC-NSCs via hydrogel injection at the T10 level 7dpi.	Improved BBB scores.	Increased oligodendrocytic differentiation. Reduced cavity area and glial scarring.	(Zarei-Kheirabadi et al., 2020)
	Oxidized HA mixed with PPFLMLLKGSTR peptide in a 20:1 ratio.	Primary human MSCs	Rat transection model	Delivery of hMSC-derived exosomes via hydrogel implantation at the T10 level immediately after injury.	Improved BBB and ladder rung walking scores.	Reduced iNOS expression and peroxidative damage. Reduced lesion size and glial scarring. Increased myelination and neurofilaments.	(Li et al., 2020)
HA	Hydroxyphenyl derivative of HA modified with RGD peptide.	Primary hUC-MSCs	Rat hemisection model	Acute: hydrogel implantation or injection at the T8 level immediately after injury. Subacutely: Delivery of hUC-MSCs via hydrogel	No significant difference in locomotor function as assessed by TSW Motion 8.5.11.	Increased axonal ingrowth. No significant difference in astrogliosis or angiogenesis. Increased expression of M1 (<i>Irf5</i> , <i>CD86</i>) and M2 macrophage markers (<i>Mrc1</i>).	(Zaviskova et al., 2018)

Table 2 (continued)

Gel	Modifications	Experimental model of SCI		Therapeutic Strategy	Observations		Ref
		<i>In vitro</i>	<i>In vivo</i>		Functional	Histopathological	
Matrigel	-	Primary mouse microglia	Mouse SCI model - injury induced by 1 mm biopsy punch	injection at the T8 level 1 week after injury. Delivery of M1 or M2 microglia via Matrigel injection at the T12 level 0, 3 or 7 days after injury.	Most significant improvement in BMS scores seen after transplantation of M2 microglia immediately after injury.	No difference in neuronal or astrocytic staining between groups. No difference in M1 mRNA between groups; increased M2 mRNA in M2 group.	(Kobashi et al., 2020)
Self-assembling peptides (SAPs)	K ₂ (QL) ₆ K ₂ (QL6)K - lysine, Q - glutamine, L - leucine) SAPs	-	Rat clip compression model	Separate injection of SAPs and NPCs at the C6 level 1 day and 14 dpi, respectively.	Significant improvement in grip strength Non-significant improvement in BBB scores, inclined plane test and cutaneous sensitivity	Reduced intramedullary cavity size. Reduced astrogliosis, tissue scarring and inflammation in perilesional area. No change in number of motor neurons.	(Zweckberger, Ahuja, Liu, Wang, & Fehlings, 2016) (Iwasaki et al., 2014)
Synthetic	F127-polycitrate-polyethyleneimine hydrogel	HAPI microglial and PC12 neural cell lines.	Rat transection model	Delivery of MSC-derived exosomes via hydrogel injection at the T10 level immediately after injury.	Improved BBB scores, significant after 35 dpi.	Reduced number of CD68 ⁺ macrophages. Reduced fibrotic scarring and apoptosis; increased remyelination and axonal regeneration.	(Wang, Kong, et al., 2021)

3.2.3. Hydrogels for exosome delivery

Exosomes, or extracellular vesicles (EVs), derived from MSC culture supernatant which act as carriers of bioactive factors (Edgar, 2016) can provide a novel approach to harness the immunomodulatory value of MSCs while avoiding the disadvantages of cell therapy. Li *et al.* designed a HA-based hydrogel that featured a laminin-derived adhesive peptide as a delivery vehicle for exogenous MSC-derived exosomes into a rat transection model. They describe how the 'adhesive' nature of the hydrogel increased the number of exosomes adhered to the gel and so delivered to the injury site (Li *et al.*, 2020), and how the treatment significantly improved functional recovery after injury and reduced expression of pro-inflammatory inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) and peroxidative damage markers (4-hydroxynonenal and 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine). Wang *et al.* fabricated an adhesive F127-polycitrate-polyethyleneimine hydrogel for delivery of exosomes derived from MSC culture supernatant in a rat transection model (Fig. 4) (Wang, Kong, et al., 2021). They found the adhesive hydrogel facilitated sustained exosome release over 56 days. This significantly reduced expression of dual macrophage/microglia markers CD68 (Fig. 4A-G) and Iba-1 (Fig. 4F-H) which improved BBB scores 35 days after injury in animals receiving the gel treatment compared to those treated with free exosomes. It should be noted that while the exosomes from the aforementioned studies were derived using similar methods, *i.e.* from MSC culture supernatants, the exact contents were not determined and positive exosome identification was only based on the presence of surface markers such as CD9 and CD63 (Li *et al.*, 2020; Wang, Kong, et al., 2021).

Overall, cell therapy presents a promising therapeutic route for SCI. MSCs and MSC-derived exosomes are of particular interest from an immunomodulatory perspective (Cofano *et al.*, 2019; Lankford *et al.*, 2018). The optimal hydrogel for cell therapy contains adhesive motifs, *e.g.* laminin-derived peptides, to enhance the adhesion of cells to the hydrogel matrix, improving cell graft survival and localization to the injury site (Papa *et al.*, 2018). Clinical translation of hydrogel-based cell therapy is a costly and time-consuming process, so in the following section

we describe recent applications of hydrogels as drug delivery vehicles as an alternative treatment strategy for SCI.

3.3. Hydrogels for effective delivery of drugs

Clinical translation of established therapeutic agents for SCI treatment is challenging. Firstly, the majority of systemically administered drugs are unable to reach the injury site due to the impermeability of the blood-spinal cord barrier (Upadhyay, 2014). Those that can in principle bypass this barrier most often require parenteral/systemic administration, given their typically short circulation half-lives, in high doses and/or with high frequency, to reach therapeutic concentration at the injury site. This can lead to deleterious side effects (Gerndt *et al.*, 1997) and may contribute to ongoing inflammatory activation. Hydrogels can help address this challenge by providing sustained and localized release of molecules directly at the injury site (Lin & Metters, 2006). Hydrogels can be designed to act as delivery vehicles for the drug cargo themselves, or to act as carriers for drug-loaded particles/carriers. A wide variety of different drugs have been delivered using hydrogels for SCI and have displayed anti-inflammatory effects, including biologics (*e.g.* BDNF), small molecule drugs (*e.g.* baricitinib) and steroids (*e.g.* methylprednisolone). The current state of release of molecules from hydrogels in SCI with immunomodulatory effects is provided in Table 3, which we will refer to and discuss in the following subsections.

3.3.1. Hydrogels for sustained immunomodulatory drug release

The timing of immunomodulatory therapies should be considered when designing hydrogels for SCI, as the secondary inflammatory response can persist for months after the initial primary injury (Fleming *et al.*, 2006). Ideally, hydrogels for SCI treatment should deliver a therapeutic dose to counteract the onset of the inflammatory response, with sustained delivery over a period of weeks to months. Growth factors have shown promise in preclinical SCI models, however they are

Fig. 4. MSC-derived exosomes delivered by a PCE-based hydrogel reduce inflammation in a rat transection SCI model. (A, B) Images and quantification of CD68 and GFAP staining at 56 dpi. CD68⁺ cell counts from in (C) margin, (D) epicenter, and (E) caudal end of the spinal cord. (F–H) CD68 and Iba-1 expression in each group. (I) Iba-1 immunostaining of microglia/macrophages *in vitro*. (J) Quantification of Iba-1⁺ microglia/macrophages from I. Reproduced under open access agreement from (Wang, Kong, et al., 2021).

protein-based therapeutics that are easily degraded when administered systemically. This can be mitigated by using a hydrogel system for spatiotemporally controlled delivery directly to the injury site. Seeking to utilize the affinity of many growth factors for heparin in order to design a sustained and localized hydrogel delivery system, Wang *et al.* synthesized a laponite hydrogel modified with heparin and demonstrated sustained release of FGF4 over 35 days *in vitro* (Wang *et al.*, 2019). This resulted in a reduced number of CD68⁺ microglia/macrophages and improved functional recovery in a rat compression SCI model. Similarly, Wang *et al.* demonstrated in a rat contusion model that BDNF and docetaxel delivery via heparin-modified poloxamer hydrogel significantly improved BBB scores and polarized macrophages towards the M2 phenotype, as shown by CD206⁺ immunofluorescent staining (Wang *et al.*, 2018). Some immunomodulatory cytokines also display affinity for heparin. Schirmer *et al.* developed heparin-based cryogel microcarriers for delivery of IL-13 to the mouse brain, which may hold potential for a similar system to deliver anti-inflammatory cytokines in an SCI model (Schirmer *et al.*, 2020).

PLGA-PEG-PLGA hydrogels are synthetic biocompatible, thermosensitive and have been used to deliver various immunomodulatory compounds. For example, Atsttrin is an engineered progranulin derivative that has anti-inflammatory properties. Wang *et al.* described the delivery of this molecule to a mouse contusion model using a PLGA-PEG-PLGA hydrogel, and found reduced expression of

pro-inflammatory iNOS and p-p65 and improved functional recovery (Wang, Zhang, et al., 2019). Similarly, delivery of the FDA-approved JAK1/2 inhibitor baricitinib using a PLGA-PEG-PLGA hydrogel led to decreased expression of iNOS and TNF- α and improved functional recovery (Zheng *et al.*, 2021). PLGA-PEG-PLGA gels are thermoresponsive at physiological temperature which allows for drug loading in the solid state and steady drug release upon injection. Other options for controlled drug release from hydrogel matrices include the incorporation of drug-loaded carriers.

3.3.2. Hydrogels and microparticle drug carriers

Sustained drug release can be achieved by using drug carriers, most commonly micro-or nanoparticles (e.g. PLGA), suspended in the hydrogel matrix. Nazemi *et al.* encapsulated the poorly water-soluble drug Paclitaxel in PLGA microspheres and incorporated with minocycline hydrochloride into the matrix of an alginate hydrogel (Nazemi *et al.*, 2020). Sustained release of both drugs was achieved over eight weeks *in vitro*, while reduced inflammation and scar tissue formation, increased axonal regeneration and improved functional improvement were observed for the treatment group in a rat hemisection model. Papa *et al.* designed a polymeric nanoparticle system for selective administration of drugs to activated microglia/macrophages in a mouse clip compression model using an agarose/carbomer hydrogel (Papa *et al.*, 2014). Nanoparticle internalization was achieved by clathrin-

Table 3
Applications of hydrogels as delivery vehicles of bioactive molecules with immunomodulatory effects for SCI.

Gel	Modifications	Experimental model of SCI		Therapeutic Strategy	Observations		Ref
		<i>In vitro</i>	<i>In vivo</i>		Functional	Histopathological	
Agarose	Agarose carbomer copolymer hydrogel with poly(methyl methacrylate) nanoparticles added at 1%.	Primary mouse microglia and neuron/glia co-cultures	Mouse clip compression model	Delivery of microglia-targeted nanoparticles <i>via</i> hydrogel injection at the T11 level 24 h after injury.	No significant difference in BMS scores.	Nanoparticle internalization by microglia was increased in LPS-stimulated co-cultures. Nanoparticles were selectively internalized by microglia <i>in vivo</i> .	(Papa et al., 2014)
Alginate	Addition of paclitaxel-loaded PLGA microspheres to reach a drug concentration of 179.2 mg/mL.	–	Rat hemisection model	Delivery of minocycline hydrochloride and paclitaxel <i>via</i> hydrogel injection at the T9 level immediately after injury.	Improved BBB scores.	Reduced scar formation and number of reactive microglia. Increased axonal density.	(Nazemi et al., 2020)
Chitosan-collagen	–	–	Rat dorsal column crush model	Delivery of Serp-1 <i>via</i> hydrogel injection at the T10 level immediately after injury.	Improved scores on locomotor scale based on BBB.	Reduced T-cell infiltration. Reduced expression of apoptotic markers	(Kwiecien et al., 2020)
Gelatin	Gelatin was conjugated to furfurylamine	–	Mouse compression model and mouse transection model	Delivery of engineered HGF (CBD-HGF) <i>via</i> direct injection or <i>via</i> hydrogel injection at T9 level immediately after injury.	Improved BMS scores and motor-evoked potential scores in transection model	CBD-HGF alone reduced immune cell infiltration and inflammatory cytokine expression in compression model, while CBD-HGF-hydrogel increased axonal regeneration and remyelination in transection model.	(Yamane et al., 2018)
Synthetic	Laponite mixed with heparin at 5:1, 5:2 and 5:4 weight ratios.	–	Rat clip compression model	Delivery of fibroblast growth factor (FGF)4 <i>via</i> hydrogel injection at the T9 level immediately after injury.	Improved BBB scores and footprint analysis.	Decreased lesion area, scar tissue formation, astrocyte reactivity and number of macrophages/microglia. Increased axonal regeneration.	(Wang, Gong, et al., 2019)
	Heparin-modified poloxamer with scar-targeted liposomes (no information on liposome concentration).	Primary rat cortical neurons	Rat contusion injury	Delivery of BDNF and docetaxel <i>via</i> hydrogel injection at the T9 level immediately after injury.	Improved BBB scores.	Axon regeneration and remyelination was most improved after full combinatorial treatment. Increased M2 marker expression.	(Wang et al., 2018)
	Self-assembling peptide gel triggered by alkaline phosphatase	Murine BV2 microglial cell line	Rat transection model	Delivery of methylprednisolone <i>via</i> hydrogel injection at the T9 level immediately after injury.	No functional analysis.	Non-significant reduction in TNF- α and IL-1 β expression. Reduction in hemorrhage, inflammatory cell infiltration and pseudocyst volume.	(Yu, Zhang, Zhou, Zhong, & Qu, 2020)
	PEG modified with RGD peptide with nanoparticles added at final concentration of 10% wt%	Rat C6 glial cell line	Rat contusion model	Delivery of methylprednisolone and growth factors <i>via</i> hydrogel injection at the T10 level one week after injury.	Improved BBB scores.	Reduced cavity formation, Iba-1 ⁺ and CD68 ⁺ immunoreactivity. Increased axonal regeneration and M2 macrophages.	(Ye et al., 2021)
	PLGA-PEG-PLGA commercial hydrogel	–	Mouse contusion model	Delivery of Atsttrin <i>via</i> hydrogel injection at the T10 level immediately before injury.	Improved BMS scores.	Reduced expression of pro-inflammatory and apoptotic markers.	(Wang, Zhang, et al., 2019)
		Rat HAPI microglial cell line	Rat SCI model (details not given).	Delivery of baricitinib <i>via</i> hydrogel injection (details not given).	Improved BBB scores and footprint analysis.	Decreased expression of iNOS, TNF- α and apoptotic markers. Inhibition of M1 cell morphology <i>in vitro</i> .	(Zheng et al., 2021)
		Rat HAPI microglial and PC12 neuronal cell line	Rat clip crush model	Delivery of Milk fat globule-epidermal growth factor 8 (MFG-E8) <i>via</i> hydrogel injection at the T8–T11 level immediately after injury.	Improved BBB scores.	Decreased number of CD68 ⁺ macrophages and iNOS ⁺ cells, increased number of CD206 ⁺ cells. Increased myelination and neuronal regeneration.	(Gong et al., 2020)

mediated endocytosis by activated microglia/macrophages *in vitro*, and a proof-of-concept *in vivo* study using a drug mimetic showed the system had good biocompatibility. This system could potentially deliver immunomodulatory compounds directly to activate immune cells at the injury site after SCI.

To summarize, hydrogels can be used for the successful delivery of a range of drugs with immunomodulatory effects including growth factors and small molecules directly to the injury site. Modifying the affinity of the drug to the hydrogel or using drug carriers suspended within the hydrogel matrix offers a platform for spatiotemporally controlled drug release to maximize therapeutic efficacy. Such a strategy can be combined with carefully designed hydrogel architecture to further promote a pro-regenerative environment after injury.

3.4. Combinatorial approaches

While modulating the immune microenvironment after SCI is critical for achieving functional and histopathological recovery, combining various treatment strategies may provide a tractable route to improving SCI treatment outcomes. Table 4 provides an overview of reported preclinical SCI studies that combine immunomodulatory treatments with other pro-regenerative strategies delivered using hydrogel systems.

The physical properties of hydrogels can be manipulated to create an aligned anisotropic architecture that supports linear axonal regeneration and improves functional recovery after SCI, indicating that hydrogel micro-structuring should be considered when developing functional

hydrogels (Chen et al., 2019; Milbreta et al., 2016; Yao et al., 2018). By combining an aligned hydrogel structure with MSC transplantation evidence was obtained of a neuroregenerative effect suggesting a useful strategy to promote both axonal regeneration and modulation of the immune microenvironment (Gao et al., 2013; Günther et al., 2015). Furthermore, adding neurotrophic factors to hydrogels can improve survival and bioactivity of transplanted cells (Albashari et al., 2020; Ciciriello et al., 2021). For example, Ciciriello *et al.* delivered IL-10-expressing lentiviral vectors in a hydrogel bridge within injured spinal cord to improve survival of transplanted embryonic spinal progenitor cells (Ciciriello et al., 2021). While IL-10 alone did not exert any neuroprotective effect on macrophages at the injury site, cell graft survival and axonal regeneration were significantly improved compared to control groups that lacked IL-10 or lacked hydrogel bridges.

Ma *et al.* specifically targeted the activated microglia/macrophage population in a mouse transection model by orally administering a CSF1R inhibitor, PLX3397, to induce apoptosis (Ma et al., 2020). This treatment was combined with a GelMA hydrogel implanted into the injured spinal cord to provide physical support (Fig. 5), which improved functional recovery and decreased the expression of pro-inflammatory IL1 β , IL6, TNF α , iNOS, IFN γ and CCL2 (Fig. 5G-L). He *et al.* combined BDNF with the anti-inflammatory KAFK peptide (K – lysine, A – alanine, F – phenylalanine) within a HAMC hydrogel and investigated its

effects in a rat SCI clip compression model (He et al., 2019). The hydrogel treatment reduced the expression of the pro-inflammatory cytokines TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6, increased the levels of the anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-10, and improved functional recovery. However, over 50% of the drug was released *in vitro* within the first 96 h, suggesting limitations with this approach for sustained release. These studies demonstrate that hydrogels can be used as a combinatorial treatment strategy to either deliver immunomodulatory therapies or provide structural support to the regenerating spinal cord after injury. However, many challenges and limitations remain when considering clinical translation, as described below.

4. Challenges and limitations

The type of injury model used in a preclinical SCI study affects the interpretation of results. Rodents are the most common animal model for SCI. Rats display the greatest similarity to humans in terms of pathophysiology and cellular response after injury (Sharif-Alhoseini et al., 2017), and mice provide the advantage of ease of genetic manipulation. However, differences exist in the inflammatory response between strains within each genus (Kigerl, McGaughy, & Popovich, 2006; Popovich, Wei, & Stokes, 1997). This may lead to varying results when investigating a hydrogel therapy in different strains and may also

Table 4
Combinatorial immunotherapeutic approaches including hydrogels for SCI.

Gel	Modifications	Experimental model of SCI		Combinatorial Strategy	Observations		Ref
		<i>In vitro</i>	<i>In vivo</i>		Functional	Histopathological	
Agarose	Linear channels of 166 μ m diameter.	–	Rat transection model	Delivery of BDNF-overexpressing MSCs <i>via</i> hydrogel implantation at the T3 level immediately after injury.	No functional analysis.	Axon regeneration was highest in BDNF-secreting group, but still did not regenerate beyond the gel.	(Gao et al., 2013)
Alginate	Linear channels of 40 μ m diameter.	–	Rat hemisection model	Delivery of BDNF-overexpressing MSCs <i>via</i> hydrogel implantation at the C5 level immediately after injury.	No functional analysis	Increased linear axon regeneration compared to gels with MSC/GFP. Infiltration of host cells and blood vessels.	(Günther, Weidner, Müller, & Blesch, 2015)
Gelatin	GelMA	Primary NSPCs	Mouse transection model	Microglia/macrophage regulation <i>via</i> oral delivery of PLX3397 and hydrogel implantation at the T7 level.	Improved locomotor and electrophysiological recovery	Decreased numbers of reactive microglia/macrophages and expression of pro-inflammatory factors compared to controls. Increased neurogenesis.	(Ma et al., 2020)
HA	HA modified with PPLFMLLKSTR peptide	–	Rat transection model	Delivery of BDNF-overexpressing MSCs <i>via</i> hydrogel injection at the T9 level immediately after injury.	Improved BBB scores.	Increased nerve fiber regeneration and decreased glial scarring.	(Li et al., 2018)
	HA modified with MC covalently bonded to KAFK peptide and streptavidin.	Rat PC12 neuronal cell line	Rat clip compression model	Delivery of BDNF and KAFK peptide <i>via</i> hydrogel injection at T10 level 5 min after injury.	Improved BBB scores, inclined plane and footprint analysis scores.	Reduced levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines and increased levels of anti-inflammatory IL-10. Reduced cavity volume and glial scarring.	(He et al., 2019)
Synthetic	PF127 poloxamer modified with heparin	Primary dental pulp stem cells (DPSCs), mouse RAW 264.7 macrophage cell line	Rat clip compression model	Delivery of bFGF and DPSCs <i>via</i> hydrogel injection at T9 level immediately after injury.	No functional analysis.	bFGF reduced IL-6 expression in DPSCs <i>in vitro</i> . DPSCs increased RAW264.7 M2 morphology <i>in vitro</i> . Decreased expression of IL-6 and TNF- α and increased axonal regeneration <i>in vivo</i> compared to controls.	(Albashari et al., 2020)
	Hydrogel tubes formed from PEG maleimide	–	Mouse hemisection model	Delivery of IL-10 expressing lentiviral vectors <i>via</i> hydrogel bridge implantation at the C5 level immediately after injury, followed by injection of E14 spinal progenitor cells 14 dpi.	Improved scores in the horizontal ladder beam test.	No significant difference in total or M2-specific macrophage infiltration across all groups. Decreased glial scarring. Increased cell graft survival, neuronal differentiation, axonal elongation and remyelination compared to controls.	(Ciciriello et al., 2021)

Fig. 5. A combination therapy of GelMA hydrogel with microglial depletion and repopulation (MDR) using PLX3397 attenuates inflammation in a mouse transection SCI model. (A) Resting Iba1⁺ microglia appear ramified and active cells appear bushy. Quantification of ramified/resting, hypertrophic and active/bushy microglia/macrophage in (B) Control, (C) Gelatin, (D) MDR, and (E) MDR + Gelatin groups. (F) Quantification of the number of CD68⁺ cells. (G-L) mRNA expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL6, TNF α , CCL2, IFN γ , iNOS, and IL1 β) at day 60 post-treatment. * $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$. Adapted with permission from (Ma et al., 2020). Copyright © 2020 Elsevier.

introduce barriers when comparing results of one study to another. The vertebral level of the injury should also be noted, as cervical and upper thoracic injuries lead to more severe motor and sensory defects and thus functional recovery may be limited in these models. To further complicate matters, the neuroanatomical-functional paradox describes how lesions of comparable size can produce different levels of both functional impairment and subsequent recovery depending on the location of the lesion. This highlights the importance of implementing a standardized injury model when testing the efficacy of hydrogel therapies (Fouad, Popovich, Kopp, & Schwab, 2021).

Clinically, the treatment of SCI is further complicated by the heterogeneous injury presentation in the patient population in terms of lesion size, shape, and severity. Pre-formed hydrogels (*i.e.* hydrogels that are crosslinked *ex vivo* and implanted into the injured cord) are commonly used in studies that focus on axonal regeneration using a transection injury model (Günther et al., 2015; Khaing et al., 2011; Yao et al., 2018). This injury model mimics the clinically rare laceration injury, and does not accurately represent the irregularly shaped lesion formed in the common contusion/compression injury (Kang et al., 2018). Furthermore, almost 70% of SCIs are classified as ‘incomplete’ which implies

that there is some level of tissue preservation in the injured spinal cord (*Facts and figures at a glance*, 2019). Surgical implantation of a pre-formed hydrogel block is an invasive technique which risks further damage to spared tissue. Injectable hydrogels are a less invasive and more suitable alternative to pre-formed hydrogels, as they can fill an irregularly shaped lesion (Macaya & Spector, 2012). This however limits the possibility of pre-made architectures, which can improve guided axonal regeneration. Additionally, identifying the optimal injection site may be difficult in the acute stage when the lesion is undefined, or in the chronic stage when the glial scar acts as a physical barrier preventing the entry of therapeutics to the injury site. Hydrogels containing liposomes with a scar-targeting tetrapeptide showed good localization to the injury site following injection in a rat contusion model immediately after injury (Wang et al., 2018), demonstrating the possibility of manipulating the targeting properties of peptides to localize an injected therapy to the desired injury site even in the acute phase. Furthermore, Huang *et al.* demonstrated that surgical scar removal prior to hydrogel implantation four weeks post injury in a rat transection model significantly improved axonal regeneration and functional recovery, showing that hydrogel therapies can be effective even in the chronic phase (Huang et al., 2020).

Fig. 6. Ideal physical properties and therapeutic additions to hydrogels for SCI. The factors listed in this diagram can be used alone or in combination with each other to design a functional hydrogel system for SCI repair. Created with Biorender.com.

During development of an injectable hydrogel therapy, the gelation method should also be carefully considered. Hydrogels that rely on photoinitiated crosslinking for gelation may not be suitable in a clinical setting due to the exposure of living tissue to UV light (Nezhad-Mokhtari, Ghorbani, Roshangar, & Soleimani Rad, 2019). Hence, thermoresponsive hydrogels that gel *in situ* at physiological temperature, may offer a more translatable repair strategy for SCI (Hong et al., 2017; Li et al., 2019; Zheng et al., 2021). Furthermore, the ideal hydrogel should be biodegradable (with non-toxic by-products) over an extended but predictable timeframe. During this time, the hydrogel would be invaded by host cells, eventually leaving behind healthy regenerated tissue at the original injury site.

Most preclinical studies apply a hydrogel therapy immediately after injury (see Tables 1-4), which presents an obvious limitation in terms of translational potential, since patients would not present to physicians in the immediate minutes after injury. The role of timing in SCI treatment is an important factor to consider when designing a therapy, especially given the extended timeframe of events during the secondary injury phase and the different cell types present during injury phases (Saghazadeh & Rezaei, 2017; Silva et al., 2014). Hydrogel-based delivery of a drug targeted to neutrophils for example, would be most useful delivered within 24 h after injury while it can be anticipated that a drug targeting monocytes should be delivered one week after injury in a sustained release mode over several subsequent weeks (Donnelly & Popovich, 2008). Considering the timescale of events, systemic immunological therapies targeting monocytes or directly repolarizing macrophages are an exciting avenue of study, for which injectable hydrogels used post-operatively are an appealing approach.

5. Conclusions and future perspectives

SCI remains a significant therapeutic challenge due to the complexity of the SCI microenvironment and varied mechanisms (and thus presentation) of injury. Conventional therapeutic approaches fail to reconnect disrupted neural circuitry and thus motor or sensory deficits experienced by SCI patients persist. Some biomaterial scaffold systems exist that have shown safety and efficacy in human SCI patients. The Neuro-Spinal Scaffold is a polymeric bioresorbable scaffold that was tested in patients with complete thoracic SCI (Kim et al., 2021). Seven

of 16 patients experienced an improvement in ASIA Impairment Scale (AIS) scoring from Grade A (complete injury) to Grade B or Grade C (incomplete injury). Additionally, the collagen-based NeuroRegen scaffold was loaded with hUC-MSCs and implanted into eight patients with chronic complete SCI (Zhao et al., 2017). No adverse effects were observed, and each patient experienced some form of improvement in sensory, motor, or autonomic tests. However, no improvement in ASIA scoring was observed. These studies demonstrate that biomaterial-based treatments can improve recovery in clinical SCI cases, however, there are currently no clinically approved hydrogels in use for SCI which highlights a significant unmet clinical need for SCI patients. While some bio-derived hydrogels exist for dermal and osteoregenerative applications (Mandal, Clegg, Anselmo, & Mitragotri, 2020), inherent limitations in the reproducibility of bio-derived materials limits their use in the clinic. One possible solution, is to take the features of these materials which have been described for SCI throughout Section 3, *i.e.*, cell adhesive motifs, porous structure, *etc.*, and derive synthetic analogues that can be reliably reproduced on a mass scale. As recently summarized by Correa and co-workers on a broader scale, and by ourselves in relation to SCI, translational hydrogels present numerous opportunities to address this gap in the clinical SCI field (Correa et al., 2021).

In light of our findings, in Fig. 6 we present a summary of the ideal physical properties of translational hydrogels for SCI repair. This includes a biocompatible and biodegradable material with a porous and aligned architecture to support molecular mobility and linear axonal regeneration within the hydrogel. Given currently available fabrication and the state-of-the-art in synthesis, such materials are achievable on small scale. Unfortunately, certain hurdles still exist for clinical translation, including proper sterilization/or production in sterile environments, batch-to-batch reproducibility and hence scaled production. Furthermore, delivery of MSCs and/or NSCs is recommended to remodel the injury microenvironment and replace damaged neural cells. A combination of both cell types is more effective than simple cell replacement (Zhou et al., 2020). Additionally, iPSCs alone and with hydrogels are emerging as a novel approach in preclinical SCI studies and may replace the use of NSCs as they are more easily sourced from an ethical standpoint (Fan et al., 2018; Joung et al., 2018; Qin et al., 2018). The development of autologous cell transplants this way offers a personalized

therapeutic approach that can be tailored to each patient (Anderson et al., 2017; Dai et al., 2013; Tabakow et al., 2013). However, complications still exist in this field in the way of uncontrolled differentiation and tumorigenesis and these issues need to be addressed before iPSCs can be applied in the clinic on a meaningful scale (Itakura et al., 2015; Tsuji et al., 2019). While not discussed in detail in this review, the glial scar acts as a major physical barrier to regeneration after SCI and can be targeted by anti-inhibitory molecules that impede CSPG deposition (Silver & Miller, 2004). Hydrogel-based systems that specifically target the glial scar in this way have shown efficacy in preclinical SCI studies (Raspa, Carminati, Pugliese, Fontana, & Gelain, 2021; Wilems & Sakiyama-Elbert, 2015). For example, delivery of the anti-inhibitory molecule chondroitinase ABC from a self-assembling peptide hydrogel significantly reduced glial scarring and improved BBB scores in a rat contusion model (Raspa et al., 2021). Combining this approach with immunomodulatory therapies may be necessary in chronic SCI cases to bypass the inhibitory effects of the glial scar and further improve the injury microenvironment for axonal regeneration. Suitable therapeutics, such as growth factors and anti-inflammatory drugs (see Table 3) can be incorporated using micro/nanoparticle carriers or affinity-based systems, e.g. heparin. Although clinical translation remains a challenge, by combining a functional immunopharmacological-hydrogel with gold standard physiotherapy and rehabilitation efforts (Hicks et al., 2011), one could offer a multi-component approach to revolutionize the clinical SCI field and significantly improve outcomes for SCI patients worldwide.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest. The material described in the manuscript is the work of the authors and is not simultaneously under consideration by any other journal. All authors declare that they agree to submit this manuscript to *Pharmacology and Therapeutics*.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by University College Dublin, Science Foundation Ireland (16/IA/4584 to DB and 19/FFP/6642 to DD), the European Union's Horizon 2020 (H2020-MSCA-IF-2019) research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement 893099 – ImmunoBioInks to JW and an Irish Research Council Government of Ireland Postgraduate Scholarship (GPIPG/2021/304) to CW.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pharmthera.2021.108043>.

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